

NOTES

anode compartment anodic hydrogen is obtained; H_2O^+ decomposing in the cathode compartment is responsible for the observed oxygen at the cathode. An encounter with an oppositely charged ion particularly H^+ and OH^- ions may also cause the same kind of gas liberation at the wrong electrode. Details are none too clear but the results oblige us to think that there must be some other concurrent kind of mechanism of current conduction different from that proposed by Hittorf which is responsible for these anomalous observations; this latter mechanism is probably connected with ions derived from water. It is quite likely that this hitherto unknown mechanism is responsible for the fact³ that explosive mixtures of hydrogen and oxygen are liberated at both cathode and anode on electrolysis of sodium or potassium sulphate solutions at higher temperature even for strong solutions at fairly high current density.

References

1. SANTI R. PALIT, "Chemistry", 1975, Vol. 48, p. 16.
2. SANTI R. PALIT and SAMITA CHAUDHURI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 104.

Synthesis of Cyclohepta[b]Thiophen Derivatives. Part-II

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OVER the last twenty years there has been a growing interest in the use of 2- and 3-substituted thiophenes in medicinal chemistry¹. Raney nickel desulphurization of thiophenes has also been developed as an important tool for the synthesis of aliphatic compounds². In connection with our programme on dehydrogenation studies of spiro compounds having a cycloheptane ring³ and on desulphurization reaction, several cyclohepta[b]thiophen derivatives were needed. Here we report the synthesis of 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen-4-one (7), 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen (10) and their alkyl derivatives by an adaptation of the method developed earlier⁴. Recently, synthesis and photochemical behaviour of cyclohepta[b]thiophen-4-ones were reported⁵.

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Friedel-Craft condensation of cyclohexane-1,1-diacetic anhydride with thiophen gave the keto acid (1) which was reduced by Huang-Minlon procedure to the pentanoic acid (4). The acid chloride of the reduced acid was cyclised using stannic chloride to give the cyclic ketone (7). The cyclic ketone was reduced by Huang-Minlon procedure to the spiran (10). In a similar manner, 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-2-methyl-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen (11) and 5,6,7,8-tetrahydro-2-ethyl-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen (12) were synthesised starting from appropriate alkylthiophen and cyclohexane-1,1-diacetic anhydride. The structures of the keto acids (1-3) and cyclohepta[b]thiophen-4-ones (7-9) were confirmed by spectral and analytical evidences.

Experimental

Alkyl thiophenes⁶ were prepared by the method indicated. Light petroleum refers to the fraction, b.p. 60-80. Ethereal extracts were dried with anhydrous sodium sulphate. Analytical data of the compounds (1-12) were all within experimental error.

3,3-Cyclohexane-5-(2-thienyl)-5-oxopentanoic acid (1): To a vigorously stirred solution of thiophen (21 g; 0.25 mole) and cyclohexane-1,1-diacetic anhydride (45.5 g; 0.25 mole) in nitrobenzene (200 ml) at 0° was added anhydrous aluminium chloride (63 g; 0.5 mole) slowly in parts. The mixture was stirred further for 1 hr, hydrolysed with ice and hydrochloric acid, and steam distilled to remove the solvent. The crude product after filtration was dissolved in sodium carbonate solution, charcolised and finally acidified with conc. HCl. The solid product was obtained by filtration and on recrystallisation from light petroleum gave the keto acid (1), m. p. 103° (46 g, 69%). ν_{max} (KBr): 1640 and 1690 cm^{-1} ; δ : 1.4 (10H, s), 2.7 (2H, s), 3.1 (2H, s), 7.2 (1H, m), 7.7 (2H, m) and 11.2 ppm (1H, s).

3,3-Cyclohexane-5-(2-thienyl) pentanoic acid (4): The keto acid (1) (13.3 g; 0.05 mole) was reduced by Huang-Minlon procedure⁷ using diethylene glycol (56 ml) potassium hydroxide (9.87 g) and ~99% hydrazine hydrate (10.7 ml). The pentanoic acid (4) distilled at 190/0.7 mm and slowly solidified, m.p. 75° (7.9 g, 62.7%).

5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen-4-one (7): To a solution of 4 (13.86 g; 0.055 mole) in ether (50 ml), purified thionyl chloride (8.8 ml) and pyridine (several

drops) were added. The mixture was refluxed for 5 hr after which the solvent and excess thionyl chloride were removed *in vacuo*. The crude acid chloride was dissolved in dry carbon disulphide (200 ml) and cooled to 0°. Stannic chloride (12.1 ml) was added dropwise with vigorous stirring and the mixture was allowed to come to room temperature and stirred for another 2.5 hr. After hydrolysis with ice and hydrochloric acid, the organic layer was separated, washed with dil. HCl, water, sodium bicarbonate solution, and then again with water and finally dried and distilled to give the cyclohepta[b]thiophenone (7) which slowly solidified, b.p. 165°/1 mm, pale yellow solid, m.p. 65° (8 g, 62%). λ_{\max} 256 (log ϵ 3.85); ν_{\max} (KBr): 1660 cm^{-1} ; δ : 1.4 (10H, s), 1.75 (2H, t), 2.55 (2H, s), 2.9 (2H, t), 7.0 (1H, d) and 7.3 ppm (1H, d). 2,4-DNP derivative of 7 was crystallised from ethyl acetate-alcohol mixture, m.p. 178-180°.

5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen (10): The ketone (7) (5.46 g; 0.023 mole) was reduced by Huang-Minlon procedure, as described earlier using diethylene glycol (28 ml), potassium hydroxide (4.5 g) and ~99% hydrazine hydrate (5.5 ml). After usual work-up the reduced product (10) distilled at 122°/0.4 mm (4.95 g, 96.4%).

3,3-Cyclohexane-5-(5-methyl-2-thienyl)-5-oxopentanoic acid (2): Prepared as described for the keto acid (1) from 2-methylthiophen and cyclohexane-1,1-diacetic anhydride in 86% yield, m.p. 100° (from benzene-light petroleum), ν_{\max} (KBr): 1640 and 1690 cm^{-1} ; δ : 1.4 (10H, s), 2.4 (3H, s), 2.5 (2H, s), 3.0 (2H, s), 6.7 (1H, d), 7.5 (1H, d) and 11.0 ppm (1H, s).

3,3-Cyclohexane-5-(5-methyl-2-thienyl)pentanoic acid (5): Prepared by Huang-Minlon reduction of 2 by the method described earlier in 83% yield. The acid (5) had b.p. 186°/1.1 mm. It slowly solidified on cooling, m.p. 52°.

5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-2-methyl-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen-4-one (8): The reduced acid (5) was converted to the acid chloride by thionyl chloride method and finally cyclised to the cyclic ketone (8) by stannic chloride in 80.7% yield. It had b.p. 155°/0.8 mm and slowly solidified on cooling, m.p. 90°. λ_{\max} 257 (log ϵ 4.0); ν_{\max} (KBr): 1655 cm^{-1} ; δ : 1.4 (10H, s), 1.75 (2H, t), 2.3 (3H, s), 2.55 (2H, s), 2.9 (2H, t) and 6.95 ppm (1H, s). 2,4-DNP derivative of 8 was crystallised from ethyl acetate-alcohol mixture, m.p. 227°.

5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-2-methyl-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen (11): The cyclic ketone (8) was reduced by Huang-Minlon procedure to give the spiran (11) in 93% yield, b.p. 145°/1.2 mm.

3,3-Cyclohexane-5-(5-ethyl-2-thienyl)-5-oxopentanoic acid (3): Prepared from 2-ethylthiophen and cyclohexane-1,1-diacetic anhydride in 90% yield. The keto acid (3) crystallised from light petroleum, m.p. 88°; ν_{\max} (KBr): 1640 and 1690 cm^{-1} ; δ : 1.2 (3H, t),

1.4 (10H, s), 2.75 (2H, s), 2.8 (2H, m), 3.0 (2H, s), 6.8 (1H, d), 7.55 (1H, d) and 11.0 ppm (1H, s).

3,3-Cyclohexane-5-(5-ethyl-2-thienyl)pentanoic acid (6): Reduction of the keto acid (3) by Huang-Minlon procedure gave the reduced acid (6) in 82% yield, b.p. 195°/1.2 mm.

5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-2-ethyl-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen-4-one (9): The reduced acid (6) was converted to the acid chloride by thionyl chloride method and finally cyclised to the cyclic ketone (9) by stannic chloride in 80% yield, b.p. 165°/0.8 mm. λ_{\max} 258 (log ϵ 3.9); ν_{\max} (KBr): 1650 cm^{-1} ; δ : 1.2 (3H, t), 1.4 (10H, s), 1.75 (2H, t), 2.6 (2H, s), 2.65-2.95 (4H, m) and 7.0 ppm (1H, s). 2,4-DNP derivative of 9 was crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 152°.

5,6,7,8-Tetrahydro-2-ethyl-6,6-spirocyclohexane-4H-cyclohepta[b]thiophen (12): Huang-Minlon reduction of the cyclic ketone (9) gave the spiran (12) in 92% yield, b.p. 158°/1.2 mm.

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References

- (a) L. S. TULLER, J. W. PRATT and F. S. YATES, *Manufacturing Chemists and Aerosol News*, 1978, **49**, May and June.
- (b) R. J. GILLESPIE and A. E. A. PORTER, *J. Chem. Soc. Perkin I*, 1979, 2624.
- "Synthetic Reagents", (Ed.) J. S. PIZZY, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., Vol. 2, p. 175.
- S. C. SEN GUPTA and P. K. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 660.
- P. K. SEN, B. KUNDU and T. K. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 847.
- G. JONES and M. J. ROBINSON, *J. Chem. Soc. Perkin I*, 1977, 505.
- J. V. HEID and R. LEVINE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1948, **13**, 409.
- Org. Syn.* (Ed.) N. RABJOHN, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., Coll. Vol. IV, p. 510.

Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of 2-Phenyl-2-(2-hydroxy-3'-5'-dichlorophenyl)-3-N-amino-sulphophenyl/4-methyl pyrimidyl/-4, 6-Dimethyl pyrimidyl/3-(N'-2-thiazolylsulphanilamido)-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones and their Benzoyl Derivatives

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4-THIAZOLIDINONE derivatives have been found to possess wide variety of physiological properties viz., anticonvulsant¹, sciatic nerve block², spiral anaesthesia³, CNS stimulant⁴, local anaesthetic⁵, analgesic⁶, sedative⁶, choleric⁶ and antiphlogistic⁷.